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Increase Student Interest and Ease in Learning via Using Augmented Reality for Medical Devices in Teaching

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Abstract:	<p>Background</p> <p>Improving student performance and student interest in theoretical concepts is fundamental to achieving optimum learning development. The present study intends to evaluate the effect of using Augmented Reality (AR) with Simulation on student performance and student interest in the classroom.</p> <p>Method</p> <p>All students were requested to join a department-scale educational research study that involve AR using their smartphones within their classes. A custom-designed questionnaire was handed to students after a demonstration of the present study before a familiarization session was also conducted.</p> <p>Results</p> <p>A total of 77 students voluntarily participated in the current study, both males (n=47) and females (n=30). Interestingly, 70% of the participating students were mostly 3rd-year and 4th-year students. A strong and positive association was witnessed for most of the answers, hence the majority of students recommend applying AR technology for studies. Furthermore, students' responses indicated that using AR technology increased educational content, understanding, and user-friendliness of the interface, and should be applied across all other subjects.</p> <p>Conclusion</p> <p>The AR technology suggests a potential tool to increase student learning and student engagement and also achieve a better outcome for theoretical concepts, especially in low-income countries.</p>
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COVERING LETTER

**To,
The Respected Editor-in-Chief
Evaluation and Program Planning**

Dear Madam,

I am submitting a new scientific work, titled “**Increase Student Interest and Ease in Learning via Using Augmented Reality for Medical Devices in Teaching**” for consideration of publication in the journal of “*Evaluation and Program Planning*”.

Improving student performance and student interest in theoretical concepts is fundamental to achieving optimum learning development. The present study intends to evaluate the effect of using Augmented Reality (AR) with Simulation on student performance and student interest in the classroom. A strong and positive statistically significant association was witnessed for most of the answers, hence the majority of students recommend applying AR technology for studies. Furthermore, students’ responses indicated that using AR technology increased educational content, understanding, and user-friendliness of the interface, and should be applied across all other subjects. The AR technology suggests a potential tool to increase student learning and student engagement and also achieve a better outcome for theoretical concepts, especially in low-income countries.

The manuscript has not been previously published and is not been submitted elsewhere. If accepted, it will not be published elsewhere, without the written consent of the copyright-holder. All authors have approved the manuscript and agree with its submission to the journal of *Evaluation and Program Planning*.

I hope that the reviewing process finds the manuscript acceptable for publication in the journal.

Thank you.

Sincerely Yours,

Ravish Javed

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HIGHLIGHTS

Improving student performance in studies to optimize learning

The majority of students recommend using Augmented Reality technology for studies

Students indicated using Augmented Reality technology increased educational interest

Augment Reality technology suggests a potential tool to increase student learning

Increase Student Interest and Ease in Learning via Using Augmented Reality for Medical Devices in Teaching

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ABSTRACT

Background: Improving student performance and student interest in theoretical concepts is fundamental to achieving optimum learning development. The present study intends to evaluate the effect of using Augmented Reality (AR) with Simulation on student performance and student interest in the classroom.

Method: All students were requested to join a department-scale educational research study that involve AR using their smartphones within their classes. A custom-designed questionnaire was handed to students after a demonstration of the present study before a familiarization session was also conducted.

Results: A total of 77 students voluntarily participated in the current study, both males (n=47) and females (n=30). Interestingly, 70% of the participating students were mostly 3rd-year and 4th-year students. A strong and positive association was witnessed for most of the answers, hence the majority of students recommend applying AR technology for studies. Furthermore, students' responses indicated that using AR technology increased educational content, understanding, and user-friendliness of the interface, and should be applied across all other subjects.

Conclusion: The AR technology suggests a potential tool to increase student learning and student engagement and also achieve a better outcome for theoretical concepts, especially in low-income countries.

Keywords: Augmented reality, Smart technology, Higher education; Student response, Active learning

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Credit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization, O.A., and R.J.; Data collection, R.J., O.A., and M.AL.; Initial analysis, M.S., and S.A.; Funding; A. A.; Statistical analysis, R.J., and A.A.; Original draft, R.J., and M.A.; Final manuscript review, O.A., M.A., A.A., M.AL., M.S., S.A., R.J. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Data availability statement

The data presented in this study are available within the article.

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Conflicts of Interest

None.

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1. Background

A computer-generated representation of the real-world atmosphere in real-time or indirect view by information generated on the computer is classified as augmented reality (AR) (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011). With the evolution and advancement in technology, AR can now be three-dimensional (3D) with interactive and registered both in real-time or delayed format with virtual and real objects (Carmigniani et al., 2011). Additionally, AR can be in various mediums

and forms such as audio, text, video, or a combination of audio and video, and can be any other virtual augmentations with real-world objects. It is a collaborating occurrence that amplifies the current world objects or scenarios using computer-generated intuitive data. Numerous platforms (apps, hardware, software, etc.) are used by AR to display and project normal real-life content into digitally enhanced versions. Thus using AR significantly improves user familiarity and also revolutionizes the surrounding of the user into an environment that is not only interactive but also valuable in terms of understanding and learning. All sort of virtual representation of the real world or imaginary ideas falls under Milgram's Reality-Virtuality Continuum, which consists of both AR and Augmented Virtuality (AV) (Milgram & Kishino, 1994). However, AR is more practical and considered close to real-world representations and are seem to be a more effective medium for live broadcasting, conferences, and even for learning purposes. Video calling/streaming is an example of AR at its best. Thus AR plays a vital role in bringing information from the real world that is not physically present at the very moment in front of the user. It assists the user to gain experience and exposure to the real world without physical presence and physical interaction. Using AR numerous benefits can be attained in sports, communication, education, surgeries, and various others (Alzahrani, 2020). For the past few years, AR has been used for education and training (Byrick, Naik, & Wynands, 2009; Scott et al., 2008), which drastically increases the student's level of understanding in different areas and their approach to perceiving real objects.

Augmented reality is a unique combination phenomenon that combines real and virtual life. It is a technology that complements info to real life without replacing the physical medium. Once we added the data to the AR software module, the desired information or animation will appear from the AR machine. It is different from virtual reality which is computer-based and appears as a virtual environment. In most cases, AR is used to display present and future

technologies, however, it has been used to add information to real life especially to use it for simulation purposes which in-person exposure and experience is not possible (Gelenbe, Hussain, & Kaptan, 2005). For instance, the heads-up displays for most fighter planes would present information to the pilot about the speed of the plane, also the direction and attitude in 1990 (Thomas & David, 1992). Later, with the help of using AR technology, they enhanced the display by displaying an object to the pilots in the field of view and where they should lock the target (Murugan et al., 2022).

Every AR application must be built with a three-dimensional program to make the object animated or presented from all directions. During the last ten years, AR has improved significantly many companies and labs have focused on developing machines and programs that are generated by the use of AR (Manuri & Sanna, 2016; Vávra et al., 2017). In 2009, the MIT Media Lab's Fluid Interfaces Group Released SixthSense, a device that collects data from a camera, smartphone, mirror, and projector (Kumar & Pandithurai, 2013). This device consists of four sensors, the respective individual wears the sensors on his fingers that allow him to take pictures with his hands, edit the projected image, use it like a mirror, and write on the image (Kumar & Pandithurai, 2013). Later in 2013, google launched Google glass, with features of showing images, videos, and sounds onto the user's glass with real-time interaction for voice commands, and making calls based on AR, and is much easier to use for a layman (Forinash, 2015).

Accuracy and precision can be increased in the medical field by using AR, during surgeries and treatment. In the case of open liver surgery, AR is used to provide a three-dimensional model of the organ and display live images of vessels and arteries on screen in front of the surgeon (Shuhaiber, 2004). Moreover, in laparoscopic interventions, AR combined with a camera to make a navigation system that displays a live broadcast of organs and the area of interest in a three-

dimensional view (Nicolau, Soler, Mutter, & Marescaux, 2011). Medical practitioners can also benefit from AR during a surgical procedure where magnification is required (Liu et al., 2020).

Moreover, AR is not widely and commonly practiced during surgeries as this area is still grey and not matured. It still requires more acceptance by medical practitioners. In addition, dental procedures such as drilling, cutting, milling, fixation, resection, and implantation require precision and accuracy from the dentist. There is almost zero space for error as nerve channels or roots of the teeth are present without direct access to surgical targets. This makes it a big challenge to view all the structures of the target without any damage or destruction to the surrounding tissue. To overcome these issues maxillofacial surgery (OMS) was invented by using AR to cover both surgical simulation and navigation.

Earlier literature using an AR approach and student interaction provides inconclusive data. To date, there is no study documenting students' experience of AR to understand and interact with medical equipment for biomedical engineering students at the undergraduate level. Therefore, the current study examined the student response in a classroom with an AR approach using their mobile phones by just scanning a QR code or an image. Thus, the study aimed in identifying increased interest and ease in learning of the students by using AR technology. The present study highlights the benefit of using the AR approach in academia, encouraging educators to use this technology in their courses and training sessions.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design

The present cross-sectional analytical study was conducted at the *** ** Department of the *** ** ** Sciences, *** ** University. The study was exempted from ethical committee

approval, as it did not involve humans or animals to conduct an experiment or research. The study was designed to be executed in a non-complex arrangement, considering factors such as low-quality poor education and lack of facilities in lower-income countries where students and teachers are struggling for the basics (Madani, 2019). The participants of the present study were all undergraduate students of the *** ** department, who volunteered for the current study. At the end of the demonstration and AR experience, the questionnaire was shared with participating students. A total of 77 students took part and all the responses were valid and included in the data analysis.

2.2. Devices selected

The primary purpose of selecting three medical devices was to transform theoretical concepts into practical knowledge and make it easier for the students to understand. To understand external parts, working mechanisms, and the basic principles of medical devices using AR, we selected three medical machines: A centrifuge; MRI; and a Defibrillator. These devices were not physically available in the academic department for students to watch and experience to assist in learning. In addition, these specific devices fall under the domain of laboratory, imaging, and emergency (or critical care), containing mechanical and moving parts. The laboratory devices focus more on analyzing samples and separating liquid components. Medical imaging devices are used to take anatomical and functional images of the patient, through different techniques including exposures and detectors. While the emergency unit is used to provide an electrical shock to the patient.

2.3. Software application selection

extruded for 15 cm. Holes were created to hold the samples of 10 cm and we extrude cut through the sample bucket. After that, we start with the rotor and then extruded it for 18 cm Fig. 1B. The saved STL file was imported to the blender to simulate rotation at normal speed, so it can be seen easily after bringing it to augmented reality see Fig. 1D.

To add the barcode, the blender file was imported into Unity software. With the help of the software Vuforia (free to build and publish apps with a basic version), AR was created. Fig. 1E shows the barcode of the centrifuge machine so when the user uses their smartphone they see it according to what and where the object has been placed, whether it has an animation or not. After positioning the device on the barcode and everything is ready to be made as a mobile application. A Software Development Kit Package is required for android smartphones. Later Vuforia web page was used to insert our barcode and obtain a license key to use the camera. The obtained barcode package was imported into Unity software. Finally, the barcode file is ready to be sent to android phones and run our applications.

Fig. 1. (A) Blocks/buckets to hold samples, (B) Rotator for holding blocks/buckets, (C) Combined blocks/buckets and rotator inside chamber, (D) Moving blocks/bucket while holding samples and (E), Centrifuge Machine Barcode.

The earlier-mentioned protocols were followed for the Defibrillator machine. The core (or base) of the device which contains the high voltage capacitors, inductors, and the battery for storage of the energy for the portable defibrillator was modeled initially. The upper part of the core was extruded and cut for 5 mm to put the screen which shows the patient's heart signal, the level of the battery, and joule selection for the patient see Fig. 2A. Defibrillator paddles are an essential

part of the device, we modeled them in a rectangular shape with dimensions' width = 35mm, and height = 55mm, see Fig. 2B. The Blender would let us create a shock wave traveling between the two paddles to explain to the students the main concept of the devices, which is reading the ECG signal then charging the capacitors with a specific amount of joule, and then discharging the capacitors through the paddles. Following the earlier protocols Fig. 2C shows the barcode of the Defibrillator.

Fig. 2. (A) Defibrillator front view, (B) Defibrillator with moving paddles and (C) Defibrillator Machine Barcode.

For the MRI device, we followed the earlier protocol. An MRI image was drawn using SolidWorks see Fig. 3A. To view the MRI for the students but in a bigger barcode, as it'll be more realistic than a small object on a small barcode. As per our earlier protocols Fig. 3B, shows the barcode of the MRI machine.

Fig. 3. (A) Display of MRI machine using AR technology and (B) MRI Machine Barcode.

2.5. Familiarization/Induction Session

A familiarization session was held after the completion and finalizing of the AR models for all three medical devices. The prospective students attended the orientation session, in which they were briefed about AR, its advantage, and the purpose of the present study. All attendees were encouraged to ask a question and any concerns they might have with this technology and its implementation. The participation of the student was voluntary and independent without any influence from their academic teacher.

2.6. Questionnaire

A custom-designed questionnaire was used for the present study, as seen in Table 1. The questionnaire consisted of 2 demographic and 6 topic-based questions to avoid student fatigue and disengagement while answering the questionnaire (Braun, Clarke, Boulton, Davey, & McEvoy, 2021) and also considering their voluntary participation in the study. Also more focused, committed, information and qualitative responses can be obtained by any undergraduate student easily in less than 5 minutes with a short questionnaire. Therefore, saving time for the participating students and more productive and focused responses are received for the study.

Table 1

Mandatory questionnaire for every participating volunteer.

<i>No.</i>	<i>Questions</i>
1	Gender
2	Age
3	Semester / Academic level (1 to 8)

4	Does AR has an educational benefit and facilitates access to educational content?
5	If AR is included in teaching, will it help students to understand more about the medical device mechanism and the principle of working?
6	Was the application simple and easy to use?
7	Does the application usage was easy to view medical devices that were not possible to see in real life? (As students were not able to see these devices in real).
8	Do you prefer this procedure to be applied to other subjects?

2.7. Statistical Analysis

Software Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) v 28, built by IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY for windows was used. The responses ranged from 1 (highly unsatisfied) to 5 (highly satisfied). The Chi-square test was implemented to find the significant association between the responses, and ANOVA was performed to determine the level of significance between the responses with study variables such as gender, age, and academic level where all P -values less $p < 0.05$ were considered to have a statistically significant association and level of significance among the responses.

3. Results

A total of 77 students volunteered for the present study (see Fig. 4), male $n=47$, female $n=30$, with a mean age of 21.03 ± 1.70 , which can be seen in Table 2. A strong and positive statistically significant association was witnessed for most of the responses using the Chi-Square method in Table 3. Additionally, the study variables also showed a significant level of differences for a few of the responses received from the participants, which can be seen in Table 4.

Fig. 4. Gender distribution of participating students in number and percentage.

Table 2

Summary of the participants and their responses.

Question No.	Responses		
		Male	Female
1	<i>Gender</i>	47	30
2	<i>Age</i>	21.03 ± 1.70 Years	
3	<i>Semester</i>	1 st : 1	5 th : 1
		2 nd : 4	6 th : 2
		3 rd : 4	7 th : 1
		4 th : 38	8 th : 26

	<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
4	77	1	0	8	37	31
5	77	0	2	7	26	42
6	77	0	1	26	29	21
7	77	1	3	12	39	22
8	77	0	0	8	34	35

Table 3

Chi-Square Test for finding level of association within the question.

Question No.	3	4	5	6	7	8
<i>Approximate Chi-Square</i>	147.312	47.416	52.506	24.766	63.195	18.260
<i>df</i>	7	3	3	3	4	2
<i>Asymp. Sig. (p-Value)</i>	< .001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
<i>* Presence of statistically significance association for all p-values.</i>						

Table 4

Statistical Analysis between the study variables and the responses to each question.

Question No.	Independent Variables		
	Gender	Age	Semester
	ANOVA (<i>p</i> -Value)		
4	0.709	0.623	0.385
5	0.034 *	0.857	0.007 *
6	0.017 *	0.110 *	0.260
7	0.477	0.391	0.361
8	0.386	0.750	0.144
* Presence of statistically significance difference for all <i>p</i> -values.			

In Fig. 5, a highly statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) between the response was found when asked whether AR has an educational benefit and facilitates access to educational content. Almost the majority of the participating volunteers agreed, however, 40% of volunteers strongly agreed while 11% of volunteers were found to be neutral, 0% of volunteers disagree and only 1 percent strongly disagree.

Fig. 5. Participating students' response for question number 3.

When asked, if the AR program is included in teaching, will it help students to understand more about how the medical device mechanism and working? The replies displayed a high statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) between the responses. More than half of the students strongly agreed with the idea, whereas 34% of students agreed, however, 7% and 2% of students were neutral and disagreed with the question, respectively. While none strongly disagreed with the question, as seen in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Participating students' response for question number 4.

As seen in Fig. 7, a highly statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) was measured for the question response, whether the application was simple and easy to use. Here the majority of students' response was strongly agreed, agreed, and neutral with 21%, 29%, and 26%, respectively. However, 1% of the students did not agree with the question asked, also zero response was recorded for strongly disagree.

Fig. 7. Participating students' response for question number 5.

Fig. 8, displays a high statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) when asked does the application make it easy in viewing medical devices that we couldn't see in real life. The majority of the students agreed with the arrangement, similarly, 22% of students strongly agreed with the idea, whereas 12% percent of students selected neutral. However, 3% and 1% of students disagreed and strongly disagreed with the idea, respectively.

Fig. 8. Participating students' response for question number 6.

In Fig. 9, we can see a high statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) when asked whether students need this application to be applied for other subjects. The majority of the students strongly agreed with the question, while 34% agreed and only 8% of students opted for neutral as their response. However, no student disagreed and strongly disagreed with the question.

Fig. 9. Participating students' response for question number 7.

4. Discussion

The current study demonstrated the direct usefulness and positive outcome of AR technology among biomedical engineering students to learn, understand the basics, and have a 3D view of medical equipment by using their smartphones in classrooms. Moreover, it also assessed the possible outcome of AR technology likeness among students within the classroom. Using AR in classroom studies such as during lectures, practicals, experiments, etc. integrates students with visual modality as well as with auditory modality which tend to have a much better impact on the students learning than conventional studies (Huang et al., 2019). As the study was conducted voluntarily by the students of biomedical technology and no compulsion or benefits were offered to the participating students, thus the student response rate was 65.2%. The lower response rate from students could be linked to a lack of awareness of research-based studies and a lack of motivational factors. In earlier survey-based studies the same reasons were also witnessed which strengthen our findings for a lower response rate (Bursztyn, Shelton, Walker, & Pederson, 2017; Georgiou & Kyza, 2018).

By using AR technology, a positive impact was observed on students. The majority of students agree and strongly agree, 48% and 40%, respectively, when asked if AR has an educational benefit and facilitates access to educational content. The response to higher understanding could be attributed to the students having a significant personal interest and prior knowledge of AR educational benefits and content. In contrast, the neutral and disagreement response from students could be attributed to a lack of interest in AR technology which indicates the resistance to a new approach to teaching medium and could be a reluctance to learn new technology usage. Several earlier studies, also concluded that AR technology usage in the classroom tends to increase student motivation (Billinghurst & Duenser, 2012; Johnson, Smith,

Levine, & Haywood, 2010; Osadchyi, Valko, & Kuzmich, 2021; Tarng & Ou, 2012), which strengthens our findings. In contrast, a study by Jerry & Aaron interpreted that the use of AR in the classroom yielded only little but overall positive influence on students learning approaches and increased their perception of the demonstrated subject and topic (Jerry & Aaron, 2010), which is in disagreement with our findings. Furthermore, previous literature established that the learning outcomes of the student also increase with the use of AR technology which is in line with our findings (Jerry & Aaron, 2010; Lee, 2012; Tarng & Ou, 2012). Although more than half of the participating students in the study validated the question, a unanimous outcome was barely expected due to orthogonal personality traits (Singh & Singh, 2017) and other passive environmental factors (Asendorpf & Meier, 1993).

On the other hand, a large group of students strongly agree (54%) and agree (34%) that AR technology will significantly help them to understand medical device mechanisms and working. In addition, the conjunction from the majority of the volunteers' answers approves the AR technology idea that the present study is highly acknowledged by the student due to its potential positive effects on academic learning. Furthermore, some students added that the use of AR technology during lectures will increase student attention, reduce smart gadgets usage, and decrease irrelevant conversations among students. By using AR technology, time and teacher input and efforts could also be reduced.

Moreover, the students' responses indicate that using the AR technology is simple and easy to use thus displaying the success as positive among the participating students, with a significantly higher number. However, fewer students also strongly disagreed which can relate to their lack of adaptive skills to use smartphones properly, resistance to change in their surrounding environment, and trust in the currently available conventional academic resources which corroborate earlier

findings as well (Niedlich, Kallfaß, Pohle, & Bormann, 2021; Tschannen-Moran, 2017). In contrast, students willing to try new methods of learning and open to newer ideas for learning (and in general) tend to be more successful and flexible in their career and personal lives.

In addition, the majority of the participating students encouraged the idea and said viewing medical devices via AR technology is far better than seeing them in textbooks only. Though it is common in low-income countries that demonstrating theoretical knowledge in practical sessions is not carried out on real medical equipment. Drawings and dummy medical equipment are only used for the said purpose (Glewwe & Jacoby, 1994). Due to the high cost of medical equipment, relevant engineering and technical students are facilitated practical studies on obsolete medical equipment which hinders students' attention and lack of learning motivation that should be present in students studying those subjects (Akungu, 2014). A previous study outlined our point that sophisticated laboratory equipment can be costly and not feasible for the educational institute to purchase, thus AR would serve the purpose (Fjeld & Voegtli, 2002). Thus, using AR technology could overcome the economic barrier faced by students in lower-income countries by using a low-cost smartphone.

Interestingly, almost 90% of participating students advocated the idea to implement AR technology in academia, not only for understanding medical equipment basics and principles but also for other subjects wherever practical and real-life exposure is required. This could be due to internet advancement where they want to experience a visual interaction in simulated or 3D structure from their smartphones (Dogruer, Eyyam, & Menevis, 2011). Thus, a higher positive response here is due to students passively agreeing because of the influence of environmental factors, daily life experiences, and frequent usage of technology (Chen, Chang, & Hung, 2011). Earlier studies also displayed that student supported the idea of using AR technology in academia,

however, limitation always exists in terms of interpreting by individuals on their own. Thus, teachers should always be present in interpreting the outcome.

Perhaps, pedagogical access to the AR mode of teaching-learning is an advancement to display virtual objects ranging from molecules to galaxies, that smoothly deliver the theoretical concepts to students where access to practical and experimental work is not possible. Additionally, at scholastic arrangement it is often impossible to experience all objects in the classroom, thus by a little manipulation of the objects which are too small or too big in their normal day-to-day lives can be seen and comprehended during lectures or at home as well. Even though using other technologies and techniques might execute the even result, altering AR platforms delivers users a better representation of temporal and spatial concepts. Also aids in establishing the association between the displayed virtual object and the real object (Sin & Zaman, 2010).

Certain barriers do exist to hinder the use of AR technology in classrooms such as the technical expertise, electronic gadgets, and time to develop an AR tutorial for the students. Additionally, many instructors are not tech-literate enough to tackle glitches while using AR technology. Thus external support should be present to be readily given to instructors if the need arises. Also other than information technology professionals, teachers should also be trained to incorporate AR skills into their classes (Billinghurst & Duenser, 2012). Additionally, teachers should need to believe and understand that using AR technology in the classroom would benefit the learning of students, rather than using the curriculum that suits them better.

A common human perception and practice are to understand easily from illustration, whether it is in books such as drawings or flowcharts, 3D printed demonstration, video, or even in the shape of AR (Regenbrecht, Baratoff, Wilke, & applications, 2005). Nowadays the majority of students tend to have access to electronic gadgets more than ever before, thus it will surely help

them not only in their studies but also in understanding other things which are not accessible in the real world by using AR technology. Moreover, instructors nowadays have the opportunity to deliver their thoughts to the student that were not possible previously.

According to our findings, many pedagogical shortcomings can be overcome during lectures with the help of AR which is in line with earlier literature (Johnson et al., 2010; Shelton, 2002). Similarly, a study by Nouredine predicted that in a near future, AR will be adopted in education (Elmqaddem, 2019). As the present study was solely focused on one domain i.e. using AR technology to ease understanding of biomedical equipment in the *** Technology Department at *** *** University which displayed moderate to high positive responses from the participating students. Earlier literature also exhibited similar outcomes but in different contexts and domains (Di Serio, Ibáñez, & Kloos, 2013; Gradl, Eskofier, Eskofier, Mutschler, & Otto, 2016). Moreover, an earlier study stated that using AR technology at higher institutes for special needs children would be an efficient strategy to be included in education (Huang et al., 2019). However, the findings of the present study further consolidate the effectiveness of AR technology in the field of academia, especially in low-income countries where student accessibility to practical applications is limited (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017). In addition, future studies using AR technology in academia should be conducted differently by noting the impact of AR technology usage on student ability to learn the concept quickly and retain the knowledge longer. Level of literacy, gender, and age-specific studies should be designed and conducted among students in academia to help in understanding and implementing AR technology. Moreover, a future study can also be designed and conducted where students are first given a conventional lecture only (control group) and another as conventional lecture plus AR experience (test group) so a comparative analysis can be carried out.

5. Conclusion

The present study postulates an insight into using AR technology in academia for biomedical equipment at a particular scale and is the first to conduct student responses in a classroom environment from their smartphones. Commonly, new approaches are not fully welcomed and treated with great appreciation in academia. However, the majority of the students supported and accept the concept of using AR technology. The current study demonstrated the impact of using AR technology on students' responses for learning purposes. The use of AR technology exhibited a significant positive role in academia. However, future studies should be designed on a larger scale not just to increase the sample size but to consider other factors such as socio-economic condition, mental health, literacy rate of the population, both teacher and student's responses, etc. could produce different results to predict better understanding of the AR technology future in academia. Using AR technology in education and other domains would be a good and swift transformation to an eco-friendly and more sustainable and reliable approach, leaving maximum output on students with less or minimum input from their instructors.

Data availability statement

The data presented in this study are available within the article.

Conflicts of Interest

None.

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Biography

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